

Impact Assessment of High Power Electric Bus Charging on Urban Distribution Grids

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Abstract—The ongoing electrification of public bus traffic in cities improves the local air quality and can help to reduce CO₂ emissions. Besides several operational challenges, an appropriate grid integration of battery electric buses (BEBs) is crucial to maintain a safe and stable operation of the distribution grid. Increasing charging powers of up to 600 kW may complicate the situation further. The objective of this study is to evaluate the grid impacts of three different bus charging methods – *Every Station Charging*, *End Station Charging* and *Overnight Charging* – on a typical urban European distribution grid. Therefore, the charging behavior of an electric bus line was modeled with a time resolution of one second and then connected to a large grid simulation. Multiple scenario modifications have been discussed, such as increasing the number of electrified bus lines, taking into account photovoltaics, and charging in the LV grid instead. Results show that the tested grid is capable of integrating BEBs in most situations, while *Every Station Charging* causes higher simultaneity of charging and larger voltage drops than the other scenarios. Moreover, LV charging shows to be unsuitable for high power charging. To conclude, the results of the simulations offer a solid basis for considerations regarding the electrification of public bus routes.

Index Terms—EV, electric bus, grid integration, electric vehicle, heavy-duty vehicle

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of sustainable and renewable technologies into the transport sector is widely expected to be an important measure for the mitigation of global warming and to fulfill the objectives declared in the historic Paris-Agreement on climate action [1]. In 2016, the transport sector was responsible for 27 % of the total EU greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, where in the same period, road transport accounted for 71 % of this share [2]. In this context, the electrification of public road transport can help to reduce these emissions. According to [3], the replacement of internal combustion engine (ICE) buses by battery electric buses (BEBs) can curtail the GHG emissions of public bus transport by 41 % when using the

EU electricity mix. At the same time, the local air quality of cities is improved and traffic noise reduced. Similar results are obtained by [4]: In a comparison to a scenario with ICE, the introduction of BEBs in combination with energy optimization techniques results in a 51 % reduction of CO₂ emissions.

According to [5] [6], the main objectives for the electrification of public buses are accommodating present operational demands and achieving environmental benefits, while keeping the operation economically feasible. When considering an average operation time of 12 years for each BEB, the author of [7] concludes that the total cost of operation for overnight charging of BEBs is 26 % higher than for diesel buses, and 7 % higher in the case of end station charging. However, future developments in battery technology may reduce the lifecycle costs for BEBs as compared to diesel buses.

When moving towards the electrification of public transport, the integration of BEBs into the existing grid is of high importance. While there exists a significant amount of studies evaluating the grid impacts and charging control techniques of EVs in general [8] [9], corresponding analyses which focus on the grid integration of BEBs are rarely found in literature.

In one study, the public transport electrification capacity of the German city Muenster is analyzed [10]: When charging BEBs, equipped with 220 kWh batteries, at every bus stop using a charging power of 300 kW, an electrification level of 50 % of the bus routes is possible without changing any bus schedules. However, their resulting charging profiles are marked with a high intermittency, which the authors did not test in a grid simulation. Apart from charging at every station, no other charging patterns were considered, which limits the comparability of the study.

By means of a working demonstrator, [11] describes the occurrence of power quality issues with fast charging stations for BEBs and the implementation of harmonic mitigation techniques.

Fig. 1: Topology of the implemented grid model with MV EVSEs circled in blue (Double circle: Overnight charging depot). Top left: Meshed HV grid. Top right: Rural MV/LV grid. Bottom: Urban MV/LV grids.

[12] investigates the impacts on the grid, caused by several types of BEBs, such as charging at multiple electric vehicle supply equipment (EVSEs) or overnight charging. They conclude that charging at multiple EVSEs is more problematic for their test grid than overnight charging because of the high and intermittent charging power. This, in turn results in frequent tap changing, increased energy losses and voltage issues. It should be noted that due to the simulation time step of five minutes, the authors do not evaluate scenarios where the charging duration for each bus is lower than this interval. Hence, scenarios where buses are charged at every station are not analyzed.

II. METHODOLOGY

As part of the European project ASSURED [13], the grid impacts of super fast charging of full-sized electric buses in typical European cities are investigated with a simulation-based approach. According to the defined scenarios, the charging power used in the simulations ranges from 300 kW to 600 kW, with different bus charging patterns applied. These patterns are *Every Station-*, *End Station-* and *Overnight-Charging*. The following chapters describe the methodology of the grid simulation, the mobility and charging simulation and the exact scenario definition.

A. Grid Model and Simulation

A large grid model consisting of different network levels ranging from 0.4 kV up to 220 kV was implemented by means of the grid simulation software DgSILENT PowerFactory [14]. The model is based on a generic grid, developed within the scope of the project DeCAS [15] and published in the EU

H2020 project Interplan [16]. In DeCAS, grid data from four European countries was analyzed and typical urban and rural grid typologies were defined, together with appropriate power ratings, loads and generation profiles. For the simulations of this work, the data has been modified by duplicating the urban MV/LV feeder. The resolution of all profiles was improved and several new EVSEs as load elements were added. The topology of the resulting grid is depicted in Fig. 1: The meshed high voltage part of the grid consists of two 3-winding 220/110 kV transformers, each with a rated power of 100 MVA and an external grid model. The external grid controls the voltage, the angle and the frequency of the topmost node with a voltage set point of 1 p.u. (220 kV). The grid segment which this work focuses on can be seen on the lower part of the figure, where two 4.75 km long urban MV feeders with a rated current of 309 A are connected to two HV/MV transformers (both 110/20 kV; left 30 MVA, right 31.5 MVA). The right 31.5 MVA transformer additionally connects a rural MV/LV feeder. The two urban MV feeders connect 5 individually modeled LV grids and 5 equivalent LV grids via 0.6 MVA transformers. The tap changers of all transformers are disabled by default.

The grid has 270 urban LV loads, based on measured monitoring data. 70 % of these are apartment buildings, and the remaining 30 % are industrial and business facilities. They operate at a power factor of $\cos\phi = 0.95$. Power measurement data with 15 minute intervals has been used as a basis. To produce fitting simulation input with 1 second intervals, the 15 minute basis has been polynomially interpolated and polluted with artificial noise. The noise is calculated by cumulatively adding normally distributed random variables located around

zero with a variance of $1/3000$ of the maximum power to a list. The noise in the list is then linearly re-scaled to eliminate the evolved accumulated off-drift at the end of the time series. The same procedure was performed with the measured 15 minute profiles of the photovoltaic (PV) systems and the wind generators, whereby these systems are modeled as static generators. The grid includes 3 small LV wind farms with a rated power of < 0.1 MVA and two large MV wind farms with 1.4 MVA or 2.2 MVA, respectively. The PV penetration is set to 40 % of the number of urban LV loads, and the rated power of each PV system is set to 30 % of the annual maximum of the corresponding urban load, located at the same node.

The grid simulation is conducted quasi-dynamically by executing multiple balanced load flows with a time step of one second. The simulated time span is 24 hours, and the scenario handling automatically sets profiles and optionally modifies the grid.

B. Mobility and Charging Simulation

The modeling of the driving and charging behavior was focused on one specific urban bus line which roughly leads along the two MV feeders. The 20 single MV nodes act as the connecting point for EVSEs located at bus stops (loads highlighted in blue in Fig. 1). Based on statistical data from the Vienna bus network [17], the simulated driving distance between two stations is set to 0.4 km and the average driving speed is 17.7 km/h. In comparison, the line length between neighboring nodes of the MV grid amounts to 0.25 km, and therefore slight route deviations from the perfect feeder path are considered in the simulation.

The bus schedule interval is 10 minutes, and the per-kilometer energy consumption of the buses is set to 1.86 kWh/km for all scenarios except for overnight charging where 2.48 kWh/km are assumed. These values are based on an extensive evaluation of the energy demand and battery performance of city transit electric buses [18]. Since the distance between two bus stops is 0.4 km, the total length of the bus line with 20 stations is 7.6 km. Based on these assumptions, the charging time can be calculated, which depends on the defined charging power for each scenario. The charging behaviour is modeled in a way that the charging power ramps up from 0 to 100 % and down from 100 to 0 % within a few seconds to avoid large sudden steps. Provided that both driving directions are taken into account, the number of buses which operate on the route results in 8 BEBs. Power converters at the EVSEs and subsequent losses have not been modeled, and therefore the power factor is 1.

Overnight charging of buses in a depot is implemented as an agent-based simulation. This method has been chosen in order to implement two different charging control mechanisms (explained in section II-C) which require BEBs to dynamically calculate their state of charge (SOC) during profile generation. For this purpose, a comprehensive EV charging simulation as described in [19] is utilized. As the model is based on fully transient measurements of the charging process of commercial EVs, it creates charging characteristics which include the

constant-voltage (CV) phase of Li-ion battery charging. The model parameters are set according to the scenario definitions described in the following section. For the other scenarios, the CV phase is irrelevant as the buses charge for much short time periods.

C. Scenario Definition

The generated mobility patterns of the buses and the defined charging power influence the charging duration at EVSEs. In the *Every Station Charging* scenario, buses charge at each of the 20 EVSEs for 8 to 13 seconds. In *End Station Charging*, two EVSEs are active and the charging duration is 90 - 170 seconds.

Overnight Charging is performed from 0 a.m. to 9 a.m. at a central MV node (leftmost charging station in Fig. 1). The 8 buses hold batteries with a capacity of 700 kWh and arrive at the charging depot after operation with a SOC of 10 %. Due to the bus schedule, there is an arrival delay of 10 minutes between two consecutive buses. In the *CV Peak Shave* scenario, the charging power is limited to 600 kW for the whole charging depot. The *CV Cluster* scenario has 3 EVSEs at the depot, each with a charging power of 300 kW.

A typical work day in summer is simulated, and the characteristics of conventional loads, PV and wind turbines are set accordingly. The standard scenarios are executed without PV systems. Some scenario modifications are simulated as well. These are:

Low-Voltage Charging: In order to compare the grid impacts of bus charging in different network levels, additional LV EVSEs are implemented and distributed in the urban 0.4 kV grid.

Additional Bus Lines: 5 additional BEB lines which cross the simulated route are considered at 5 selected MV nodes. This is done by adding single bus stops of the added routes as new MV EVSEs located next to the already simulated EVSEs. It is assumed that the added bus lines also charge at other MV feeders which are not considered in the simulation as these bus routes only cross the evaluated grid.

PV Systems and Modified Line Lengths: To enable comparisons in more situations, the PV systems described in section II-A are activated. Furthermore, the MV main cable length between the 110/20 kV transformers and the first MV nodes have been doubled from 2.5 km to 5 km.

III. RESULTS

The analysis of the simulation results was focused on node voltages and transformer loads. At first, the 600 kW *Every Station Charging* scenario is compared with the *End Station Charging* scenario using the same charging power. The three subplots of Fig. 2 show the simulation results of *MV Feeder 1*, which is located at the bottom left in Fig. 1). The total active power of the 10 connected charging stations at MV Feeder 1 is depicted at the top. The p.u. voltage of the most peripheral MV node in the middle and the HV/MV transformer loading is given at the bottom. As can be seen in the total

Fig. 2: Every Station Charging vs. End Station Charging: Charging power, voltage magnitude and transformer loading of selected grid elements

charging power, charging at every station had a higher simultaneity factor than charging at the end stations only. While the charging power in end station charging never exceeded 0.6 MW, the frequent and short charging processes of *every station charging* accumulated up to 1.8 MW at some points of time. This was reflected in the resulting transformer loading and voltage magnitude. Nevertheless, even the voltage of the most peripheral *MV Node 1* did not sink below 0.986 p.u., whereby optional tap changers were kept disabled.

Fig. 3 compares results of the two overnight depot charging scenarios *CV Peak Shave* and *CV Cluster* by evaluating the same grid elements as in Fig. 2. Although the total charging power of the clustered scenario with 3 EVSEs at the depot was usually higher than the fixed 600 kW of the peak shave scenario, the situation also inverted at times where some buses were in the CV phase of charging, like at 02:24 and 04:48. As expected, the 8 buses were charged faster in the clustered scenario. From the grid perspective, both depot charging scenarios did not cause any issues, especially when considering the overall lower grid loading at night.

In order to evaluate if 300 - 600 kW charging of electric buses needs to be performed in the MV grid, two worst-case heat maps have been created: Fig. 4 shows the results of the 300 kW *Every Station Charging* scenarios, once applied with EVSEs in the MV grid and once with EVSEs distributed in the LV grid. There, the color coding for lines ranges from green at 0 % to red at 100 %, and the coding for nodes ranges from green at 1 p.u. to blue at 0.9 p.u. and to red at 1.1 p.u.,

Fig. 3: Overnight Charging: Peak Shave vs. 3-EVSE-Cluster: Charging power, voltage magnitude and transformer loading at selected grid elements

Fig. 4: Comparison of charging in the MV- or LV-grid. The figures only show the lower part of the full grid topology.

respectively. The deep red lines and the many blue nodes in the LV scenario (Fig. 4b) reveal that super fast charging without major grid reinforcements is not possible in the LV grid. The current and/or power ratings of the cables and transformers have been exceeded by far. For example, some of the LV main cables with a current rating of 175 A were overloaded by 250 %. In contrast, the same charging patterns with 300 kW charging power applied in the MV grid (Fig. 4a) did not cause any issues.

The scenario with five additional crossing E-bus lines has been evaluated with regard to the loading of the two 100

Fig. 5: Additional bus lines: Transformer loading

MVA 220/110 kV transformers, located in the meshed HV grid at the top left in Fig. 1. These transformers were chosen because there the collective power of all 6 bus lines would accumulate, if the *full* individual MV feeders of the additional bus lines were simulated as well. However, the results depicted in Fig. 5 only show the loading caused by one electrified bus line with the single stops of the other bus lines considered at five of the simulated EVSEs. Nevertheless, the comparison of the two *End Station Charging* scenarios in Fig. 5 shows that the crossing bus lines caused a higher simultaneity of charging, resulting in an increased transformer loading. In order to estimate the total impact of all 6 bus lines, the maximum difference between the blue and the red line in Fig. 5 can be calculated and multiplied by 6. The result is an additional transformer loading of 7.27 %. Due to the fact that the collective power of all EVSEs distributes among the two parallel 100 MVA transformers, this corresponds to approximately 14.5 MVA additional apparent power in the worst case. For a more comprehensive assessment of the effects on the HV grid, further investigations are necessary.

For *End Station Charging*, a closer look on PV generation and modified cable lengths is taken in Fig. 6, by evaluating the loading of the same transformer as in Figures 2 and 3. Additionally, the simulated node voltages of a peripheral MV node and a peripheral LV node are depicted. The result shows that when the line length of the two main MV cables (the long lines in Fig. 1) was doubled, the voltage in both network levels was only marginally lower than in the normal case. The integration of PV generation, however, showed a larger difference in the LV grid. Still, the deviations between all three scenarios can be considered as small.

IV. DISCUSSION

In all simulated scenarios, the MV grid was capable of integrating BEBs without critical issues. This, however, strongly depends on the power-, current- and voltage-ratings of the grid elements. Apparently, a combination of a 20 kV grid with strong MV cables (309 A rated current) is a proper sizing for 600 kW charging power. Moreover, the tap changers of the transformers were not needed in the simulations. Even the introduction of 5 additional bus lines only increases the loading of the two hardly burdened 220/110 kV transformers

Fig. 6: End Station Charging with PV, without PV and with increased line length: Voltage magnitudes and transformer loading of selected grid elements

by approximately 7 % compared to the base scenario without EVSEs, based on an estimation.

However, there are also some major differences between the scenarios. The short and frequent charging processes in the *Every Station Charging* scenario causes a pronounced charging simultaneity which, in turn, leads to a higher and more intermittent charging power than in the *End Station Charging* and the *Overnight Charging* scenarios. If the grid was more sensitive to power variations, the voltage drops in *Every Station Charging* would require the tap changers to perform frequent voltage adjustments. Such a behavior can significantly decrease the transformer lifetime as pointed out in [12].

The overnight charging scenarios can be considered as good grid-protecting methods due to the low charging power and high predictability. Nevertheless, the simulated BEBs required a very large battery of about 700 kWh to operate all day on this particular bus line. This can be a technical limitation for real applications. Changing the schedules in a way that buses make use of two or more charging shifts per day could decrease the necessary battery size but would also increase the required number of buses.

The severe overloading issues in the LV charging scenarios confirm that charging powers with a magnitude of 300 - 600 kW are far too high for the LV grid. Hence, MV charging is strongly recommended for super fast charging of BEBs.

It should be mentioned that simulations of other seasons than summer were out of the scope of this work. However,

winter scenarios are also of interest since they could cause higher grid loading when heating becomes relevant in living areas and in buses.

V. CONCLUSION

This study provides a comprehensive overview of the grid impacts of different charging methods for battery electric transit buses in cities. In contrast to the few available studies on this topic, the simulations performed in this work had a comparatively small time step of one second. This enabled more detailed investigations, which is especially useful in scenarios such as *Every Station Charging* where buses charge for a short time period only.

The results of the simulations show that typical European cities are probably capable of integrating several electric bus lines into their MV distribution network – at least from the grid impact perspective. For market ready applications however, many other factors must be additionally considered, such as purchase-, infrastructure- and maintenance costs as well as the technical and operational feasibility.

Future work will include additional scenario variations regarding the simulated season and grid. The grid impact of harmonics caused by charging BEBs will also be part of subsequent research.

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